

IPOs and Issue Methods: Indian Perspective

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Abstract

Firms issuing Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) in different capital markets across the world have been practicing two of the most popular issue methods: fixed price and book building method. Fixed price was the only method of pricing the IPO issues, traditionally in India till year 2000. However, owing to the benefits of book building mechanism, the trend had changed. IPO issuers in India started using book building method for pricing their issues. Thus, book building mechanism has become increasingly popular among issuers in India, especially, after year 2000. The IPO market in India during the first decade following 2000, was completely dominated by the book building mechanism. Major issuers during this period preferred book building method for pricing their issues with only a few issuers using the traditional fixed price mechanism for their issues. Such a paradigm shift in the IPO issue method was in line with the developments that took place in other major capital markets of the world.

The present study focuses on the IPOs that came to the market in India during the calendar year 2016 and the issue mechanism used by the issuers of these IPOs. The year 2016 witnessed a total of 93 IPOs in the Indian capital market. Out of these 93 IPOs, exactly two third i.e. 62 IPOs used the traditional fixed price mechanism for pricing their issues; while only the remaining one third IPOs i.e. 31 issues used book building method for pricing their issues. Such a development noticed in the IPO market in India during the year 2016, marks a major deviation from the earlier trend observed during the first decade after 2000. However, further analysis reveals that IPOs that used fixed price mechanism are small sized IPOs; while IPOs that used book building method are large IPOs in terms of funds mobilised. These large sized IPOs could achieve better price discovery for their issues through book building method which is actually one of the objectives of book building mechanism. Another very interesting observation made by the present study is that book built issues offer greater liquidity to investors compared to fixed priced IPOs. This is evident from the fact that out of 31 book built IPOs, 26 are listed on both BSE and NSE and only the remaining 5 are listed either on BSE or on NSE; while all the 62 fixed priced IPOs are listed either on BSE or on NSE,

alone. Overall, the present study finds that majority of the IPOs that came to the market in India are small sized IPOs and issuers of these small sized IPOs used fixed price mechanism for pricing their issues.

Key words: Initial Public Offerings, Capital Market, Issue Method, Fixed Price, Book Building

INTRODUCTION:

The initial capital required to commence most businesses may come from the owners or promoters of the business themselves or from their friends and relatives. However, in their journey of growth, expansion or diversification, firms need huge amount of funds which the promoters or owners themselves cannot afford. Therefore, organisations have to turn to other sources of mobilising long term funds to meet their requirements. These options may include long term borrowings from banks and specialised financial institutions, private placement, issue of debentures, issue of equity etc. Out of the many different options available in this regard, issue of equity shares to the public or what is called Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) has been a very important source of raising long term capital requirements for many organisations, worldwide.

IPOs have been quite popular mode of mobilising funds among organisations or their promoters because of many reasons. Firstly, funds raised through the issue of equity shares are usually not repayable unlike term loans taken or funds raised through the issue of redeemable debentures. Further, issue of equity shares gives an opportunity to the investors to participate in the success and growth of the issuing firms through capital appreciation or increase in the market price of equity shares, post-listing. Listing of IPO shares, which is a statutory requirement post-IPO, will enhance the liquidity of investment for the investors as these investors can sell off their shares in the secondary market i.e. through stock exchanges. Another very important reasons why IPOs are becoming increasingly popular is that they provide an exit option to the promoters. By issuing offer for sale shares, the promoters can use the proceeds of the IPO to reduce their stake in the firm and thus, use IPO as a disinvestment strategy. By issuing the shares in an IPO at a price much above the face value, the promoters can exit the venture or reduce their stake in the business at a premium to what they had earlier invested.

Traditionally, fixed price method was used by the issuers of IPOs for pricing their issues. According to this method, the issuer and the underwriter collectively fix the issue price well in advance; even before the issue is open for subscription. The investors will apply for the required number of shares of the IPO at this specific price. On the closure of the issue, the successful applicants will get the shares of the IPO at this specific price. The main drawback of this method of pricing the issue is

that the issue price is fixed even before the investors' response for the issue is made known i.e. even before the issue is open, the issue price is fixed. If there used to be very positive, overwhelming response for the issue, the issue price cannot be revised upward subsequently in the light of demand for the issue. This may create excessive demand for the shares of the issue in the grey market and the listing day price for the shares of such issue may rise sharply. As a result, such issues may experience severe underpricing; a phenomenon where the issue price for an IPO is much below the price at which the IPO gets listed on the stock exchange or the price at which the IPO shares close the listing day. This happens because the investors' potential interest or response for the issue was not considered by the issuer while fixing the price for the issue. Such underpricing causes severe loss either to the issuing company which would have mobilised more funds had the issue price been fixed at a higher level considering the investors response or to the promoters of the issuing company who would have taken away more money if offer for sale shares are included in the IPO.

To avoid such severe underpricing of IPOs, issuers in different capital markets of the world started using an alternative method of pricing the issues called book building. To some extent, book building has been successful in reducing the volume of underpricing of IPOs in different capital markets of the world.

How Book Building Helps in Better Price Discovery?

All IPO issuers in India were following fixed price route for pricing their issues until the end of late 90s. In 1995, Malegam Committee recommends book building method to discover the issue price for public issues. This price discovery was supposed to be based on demand for and supply of shares in the public issue. Following the recommendations of Malegam Committee, SEBI in 1998 framed rules for the issue of shares using book building mechanism. The book building method of pricing the public issue begins with the issuer appointing a merchant banker called Book Running Lead Manager (BRLM) to the issue. The BRLM works with the underwriters called syndicate members. These syndicate members will collect the bids from prospective investors of the issue. The BRLM is responsible for preparing red herring prospectus which will contain the price range for the issue based on valuation of the issuing company. The minimum acceptable price of this range is known as floor price. The upper price of the range called cap price is fixed at 120 percent of the floor price. Based on the response or demand the issue gets in the bidding process, the floor price can be changed plus/minus 20 percent in which case the cap price also automatically get revised. In the book building process in India, both retail investors and institutional investors can participate in the bidding process. Once the issue period is over and the bidding books are closed, the BRLM, in consultation with the issuing company, will decide the issue price.

In September 1999 the first ever Indian equity IPO with book building method came to the market. With a total of 43,75,000 shares on offer, Hughes Software Systems Ltd had successfully offered 90 percent of its total shares on offer i.e. 39,37,500 shares through book building route. The book building portion of the issue was open on September 22, 1999 and closed on September 28, 1999 in the price band of Rs.480-Rs.630 per share. Later, the remaining 10 percent shares i.e. 4,37,500 shares were offered using fixed price method. This part of the issue was open on October 7 and closed on October 12, 1999 at a price discovered by the book building earlier i.e. at Rs.630 per share. The maiden book building issue was a great success attracting application for more than 9.75 crore shares. As against the targeted Rs.275 crores from the entire issue, the book building portion itself received application for over Rs.6,000 crores at the cap price of Rs.630.

Attracted by the success of this maiden book built issue, soon many more IPO issuers in India used book building mechanism for their issues. The decade following year 2000, was completely dominated by book built issues in Indian capital market. In their study Hawaldar et al. (2018) find that out of 464 IPOs that came to the market in India between 2001 and 2011, 365 were book built IPOs and only the remaining 99 IPOs followed fixed price method for pricing their issues.

This paper is arranged as under: in the introduction section conceptual background on IPO and its issue methods, both international trend and Indian scenario, are discussed. In the second section various extant research works on the issue methods of IPO are discussed. In the third section, research objectives are discussed. In the fourth section sample, data and research methodology are discussed. In the fifth section, findings of the current study are discussed. Final section of the paper provides concluding remarks.

1.Review of Literature:

Most of the research works on two of the common issue methods i.e. fixed price and book building focus on certain important issues: which issue method results in better price discovery in the IPO process and the relationship between the size of the issue and the method of pricing the issue.

Benveniste and Spindt (1989) found that book building results in better pricing of issues and, as a result, book built IPOs face lesser magnitude of underpricing. In their paper, Chowdhry and Sherman (1996) explained a global phenomenon: large orders in IPOs usually favour book building process; while small orders prefer fixed price method of pricing public issues. Sherman (2000) in his study found that book building method provides underwriters the discretion while allocating shares in an IPO. This helps them in establishing long standing relationship with the investors. This motivates the underwriters to keep average underpricing lower in the case of book built IPOs. Study also reports that such discretion is not possible in the case of fixed price IPOs. Spatt and Srivastava

(1991) in their study found that book building method permits investment bankers to elicit information from the investors and this will help them in better pricing of the issue. Further, they found that this will result in reducing adverse selection problem among the investors. In line with the findings of Benveniste and Spindt and Spatt and Srivastava, Cornelli and Goldreich (2003) find that information collected through bids under book building mechanism helps in fixing the issue price. Ljungqvist et al. (2003) also report that book built IPOs are associated with lower underpricing in the US. Sherman (2005) highlights benefits of book building in better price discovery. His study also highlights that because of this superiority, the US based book building method has become very popular method of pricing the public issues, worldwide.

There has been good amount of research works carried on about the different methods of pricing the public issues, especially IPOs in India also. Pandey (2005) reports that book built IPOs in India are associated with lower initial returns or lesser underpricing. Ranjan and Madhusoodanan (2004) compared fixed priced and book built IPOs and report that fixed priced IPOs are associated with higher magnitude of underpricing compared to book built IPOs. In his study Bose (2005) found that book building is better than fixed price method of pricing the issues. Aggarwal (2008) found that small sized IPOs preferred fixed price mechanism and large sized IPOs adopt book building method of pricing for their IPOs. The study also noticed that book built issues are successful in achieving higher opening price on the listing day compared to fixed priced IPOs. Bora et. al. (2012) identified larger underpricing for fixed priced IPOs compared to book built IPOs; however, the difference between the two disappears when adjusted with market return. Hawaldar et al. (2018) studied 464 Indian IPOs belonging to the period 2001 and 2011 (365 book built IPOs & 99 fixed priced IPOs). They report that book-built IPOs are underpriced by lesser magnitude compared to fixed-price IPOs. As far as post-listing long run performance is concerned, the whole sample of IPOs underperform in the long run (five years). However, book built IPOs underperform much more severely when compared to the long run underperformance of the whole sample. Interestingly, the fixed priced IPOs offer positive market-adjusted returns to the investors in the long run upto five years. In another study, Hawaldar et al. (2021) found that book building has reduced the volume of underpricing in India. In their study, they found that both raw underpricing and market-adjusted underpricing for book built IPOs are less when compared to corresponding underpricing measures associated with fixed priced IPOs. They studied underpricing of 2,567 fixed priced IPOs and 367 book built IPOs belonging to the 1992-2011 period. Continuing further with the long run performance, the study finds that FP IPOs offer positive long run positive returns to the investors which are highly significant when considered one-year, three-years and five-years post-listing

period. However, the BB IPOs in their study registered significant negative returns during the same one-year, three- year and five-year post-listing period.

I. Objectives of the Study:

The present paper has the following objectives to study:

- i) To study the issue methods available to the issuers of IPO in India
- ii) To study, of the total number of IPOs that came to the market in India during the calendar year 2016, how many IPOs followed fixed price mechanism and how many followed book building mechanism
- iii) To study the relationship between issue method and size of the issue
- iv) To study the pricing characteristics of IPOs that came to market in India during 2016
- v) To study the relationship between liquidity (listing of shares in an IPO) and the issue method

II. Sample, Data and Methodology:

The present paper studies the IPOs in India that came to market during the calendar year 2016. Various information related to these IPOs like the issue method, issue price, issue size, designated stock exchange/s to list the IPO shares are gathered using the final offer documents related to the IPOs.

Firstly, on verifying the offer document section of SEBI, study finds that there is a total of 93 IPOs that came to the market in India during the calendar year 2016. Final offer documents of all these 93 IPOs are then downloaded from the SEBI website. Different sections of these offer documents are studied to collect the information needed for the study. On studying these IPOs, the issue method – fixed price or book building is obtained. ‘The Issue’ section of the prospectus provides information on the issue price, number of shares issued and the total issue size of the IPO. ‘Listing’ section of the prospectus provides information on the designated stock exchange/s where the IPO shares will be listed.

III. Findings of the Study:

On examining the 93 IPOs that went public during the year 2016, the present study finds that of these 93 IPOs, exactly two-third i.e. 62 IPOs followed fixed price method while remaining one-third i.e. 31 IPOs followed book building method for the determination of the issue price. Such a finding is a significant deviation from the recent developments in the major capital markets of the world including India. Many research

works on the issue method of IPOs, both in India and abroad, report that book building, as a method of pricing, is becoming increasingly popular among issuers and underwriters. For e.g. Sherman (2005) in his study reports that book building is becoming increasingly popular in the US as a method of pricing IPOs. Hawaldar et al. (2018) noted that of the total 464 Indian IPOs that hit the market between 2001 and 2011, 365 were book built IPOs and only 99 were fixed priced IPOs.

The following table shows the various pricing-related characteristics of the total sample of IPOs as well as book built and fixed priced IPOs belonging to the year 2016 in India:

Particulars	All IPOs (93)	Book Built IPOs (31)	Fixed Priced IPOs (62)
Issue Price (Average)	Rs.146.87	Rs.346.58	Rs.47.02
Issue Price (Maximum)	Rs.896	Rs.896	Rs.320
Issue Price (Minimum)	Rs.10	Rs.20	Rs.10
Issue Size (Average)	Rs.290.98 crores	Rs.856.47 crores	Rs.8.23 crores
Issue Size (Maximum)	Rs. 6,056.79 crores	Rs. 6,056.79 crores	Rs.49.5 crores
Issue Size (Minimum)	Rs.1.31 crores	Rs.3.96 crores	Rs.1.31 crores

The above table reveals that the average issue price of all the IPOs that came to market in India during 2016 was Rs.146.87 whereas the corresponding figures for the book built and fixed priced IPOs were Rs.346.58 and only Rs.47.02, respectively. This means, book building leads to better price discovery for the IPOs. The lowest issue price for the fixed priced IPO is Rs.10, while it is Rs.20 for the book built IPO.

The average issue size of all IPOs was Rs.290.98 crores; while it is Rs.856.47 crores for the book built IPOs and Rs.8.23 crores for the fixed priced IPOs. The maximum issue size among the book built IPOs was Rs. 6,056.79 crores, while similar figure among the fixed priced IPOs was only Rs.49.5 crores. The lowest issue size among the fixed priced IPOs was Rs.1.31 crores while it is Rs.3.96 crores among the book built IPOs. These findings on the issue size reveal that, in India, large sized IPOs prefer book building route; while issuers of small sized IPOs prefer fixed priced route for pricing their IPOs.

Finally, coming to the designated stock exchange/s where the IPO shares will be listed, study finds that out of the 31 book built IPOs, 26 of them opted to list their shares on both BSE and NSE, while only the remaining 5 planned to list on only one stock exchange i.e. either BSE or NSE. As far as the 62 fixed priced IPOs are concerned, all these IPOs planned to list on only one stock exchange

i.e. either on BSE or on NSE.

IV. Conclusion:

Issuers of IPOs in India use both the issue methods that are widely practiced in different capital markets of the world. However, findings of the present study contradict the earlier findings, both in India and abroad. Out of the 93 issuers of IPOs belonging to the year 2016 in India, only 31 (exactly one-third) of them used book building mechanism, while the remaining two-third i.e. 62 issuers preferred the traditional fixed price method for pricing their issues. Further analysis of the study, however, reveals that book building leads to better price discovery. Average, maximum, and minimum issue prices for book built IPOs are higher than the corresponding figures for the fixed priced IPOs or even for the whole sample. When it comes to size of the issue, the study finds that issuers of large sized IPOs prefer book building mechanism for pricing their issues. Once again, the average, maximum, and minimum issue sizes for book built IPOs are larger than the corresponding figures for the fixed priced IPOs or even for the whole sample IPOs. Finally, study finds that the book built IPOs are supposed to enjoy higher liquidity compared to fixed priced IPOs from the view point of investors. This is evident from the fact that out of 31 book built IPOs, 26 have proposed to list on both NSE and BSE and only the remaining 5 planned to list on only one stock exchange i.e. either on BSE or on NSE. However, all the 62 fixed priced IPOs proposed to list on only one stock exchange.

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